

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Online Music Preferences of Different Generations: an Acoustic Perspective

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Background and Motivation	1
1.2	Objectives	2
1.3	Organization	3
2	State of the art	4
2.1	Datasets	4
2.2	Music preference and age	6
2.3	Hit song prediction	8
3	Methodology	11
3.1	Materials	11
3.1.1	The LFM-1b dataset	11
3.1.2	MusicBrainz and AcousticBrainz	13
3.2	Data acquisition	15
3.3	Feature selection	15
3.4	Generation classification	16
4	Results	18
4.1	Feature selection results	18
4.2	Generation classification results	20
5	Discussion	23
5.1	Generation Classification	23

5.2	Relevant features and preference trends	25
5.3	Limitation and future work	28
6	Conclusions	30
	List of Figures	32
	List of Tables	33
	Bibliography	34
A	First Appendix	39

Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to my father and my aunt, who are always there generously supporting me.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to:

- My supervisor: Philip Tovstogan
- My co-supervisor: Dmitry Bogdanov
- Minz Won
- My family
- And all my SMC 2020 friends. We survived this unprecedented year!

Abstract

The relationship between music preferences with age is an interesting but rarely studied topic. The limited relevant research mostly concentrated on the musical genre level or a certain age group. In this thesis, we study the music preferences of different generations from an acoustic perspective, intending to understand the differences and trends in the various music tastes. We jointly took advantage of the LFM-1b dataset, MusicBrainz, and AcousticBrainz to collect the user's listening events and acoustic information. F-test feature selection and support vector machines were then used to analyze the correlation between generations' preferences and acoustic features. We finally found the most relevant acoustic features and revealed their trends along with the generation changing. For example, the younger listeners tend to listen to songs that are spectrally more complex, while the older listeners show more interest in "sad" music. We further interpreted these features, attempting to understand the reasons for these trends. Our findings suggested that some previously observed genre preferences of relevant work were associated with these acoustic features. Therefore, this thesis provides a new perspective for the study on music preferences and age.

Keywords: Music preference, Acoustic feature, Social generations

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and Motivation

People's aesthetic sense is dynamic. Influenced by education, media, and social networks, individuals' subjective feelings towards aesthetic objects vary for different generations. This difference is particularly evident in music tastes. For example, teenagers are more likely to appreciate some rebellious musicians that are considered too unconventional by older adults. There is also evidence that shows music genre preferences are substantially associated with age [1].

We are interested in this diverse relationship between music preference and age. Such an interest originates from the observation of online music listening behavior of different generations. Compared with other age groups, the young generation is a growing user group that primarily uses music streaming service [2]. Young people are highly active on the Internet, especially for entertaining purposes [3] and their daily lives are more engaged with music [4]. We believe the difference in music listening behavior between the young and old generation also includes their different music preferences. Regarding music preferences, previous studies mostly concentrated on the music genre level. However, we are concerned more about the acoustic features of music. The acoustic features include low-level ones such as loudness, spectral features, rhythm features, and high-level ones such as mood,

artist's gender, and danceability. These features may reflect the auditory experience of musical appreciation more accurately.

In this thesis, we explore the music preferences of different generations. Our division of generations is based on the sociological convention: Generation X, whose birth years are around 1965 to 1980; Generation Y (also known as millennials), who were born between 1981 and 1996; Generation Z, born after 1997. This generational theory is generally used in social science, media, and popular culture. People within the same generation might experience the same significant events and have similar ideas, problems, and attitudes. Hence, we use this theory to define each generation so that listeners of one generation share similar music preferences.

By studying each generation's preference in the acoustic features, we attempt to address two questions. First, are there any features that represent the salient properties of the music preference of each generation? Second, if there are such acoustic features, why do generations' preferences differ in them? By answering these two questions, we hope to better understand the differences in generations and the trends of musical tastes.

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of our study are consistent with the two questions aforementioned:

- The first objective is to find certain acoustic features that are significantly related to the music preference of each generation. This is essentially a feature selection task. We collect the acoustic features and rank them according to how relevant they to the generations' music preference.
- The second objective is to understand how the most relevant features are reflected in the music and why different generations have different tastes for them. To this end, we attempt to interpret these features by taking into account factors such as social influence, psychological issues [2], music production trends, etc. While this problem is still open to discussion, we believe our explanation would provide some insights for future research.

1.3 Organization

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 2 introduces the state of the art in relevant areas, including user-aware datasets for music information retrieval (MIR) tasks, music preference and age, and hit song prediction. Chapter 3 provides information about the methods and materials we adopt in our study. In Chapter 4, we present the results of the feature selection and classification experiment. In Chapter, 5 we discuss our findings, trying to answer our two research questions, and talk about the limitations of the study. Finally, in Chapter 6 we make comments on our study and summarize this thesis.

Chapter 2

State of the art

Music preference has been widely studied in sociology. However, when it comes to the relationship between music preference and age, there is not much research done. One of the reasons is the lack of a large scale dataset. In this chapter, we first introduce the state of the art datasets for MIR tasks that could provide useful materials for our study. Then we summarize the previous researches on music preference and age. Besides, there is a similar problem, hit song prediction, which is also worth reviewing.

2.1 Datasets

The rising of music streaming services has provided the listeners with zillions of music pieces. However, academic researches in MIR, especially when incorporating music content analysis, have to face the restriction of intellectual property rights. Therefore, several publicly available music datasets have been presented, enabling large scale experimentation and facilitating reproducibility. On the other hand, researchers also have access to collect data from the databases of some large on-line music platforms such as Spotify, Last.fm, and Soundcloud through their API, although it is usually a time-consuming process.

Of all these datasets, the “Million Song Dataset (MSD)” [5] is the most well-known

and widely used. As the name suggests, it contains 1 million of contemporary popular music songs, collecting their audio features and metadata, such as pitches, timbre, loudness, artist information, user-generated tags, etc. The MSD has been used in a wide range of MIR tasks, from metadata analysis to automatic tagging to music recommendation. Regarding user listening behavior, the “Echo Nest Taste Profile Subset” of MSD provides user-play counts of 1 million users on more than 380,000 songs matched to MSD, which is mostly utilized in music recommendation task.

Speaking of recommendation task, currently the largest available music recommendation dataset is the “Yahoo! Music” dataset [6]. Used to be one of the biggest music streaming services, “Yahoo! Music” possesses a huge amount of user ratings to generate recommendations. In the Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery competition (KDD Cup) 2011 contest, “Yahoo! Music” dataset was released especially for researches on music taste analysis and music recommender systems. It contains about 263 million ratings of 625 thousand music items by 1 million users, collected from 1999 to 2010. All the users are anonymized, as well as the items. So it can serve as a good testbed for collaborative filtering algorithms but may not valid for researches that need user-specific information or music domain knowledge.

Some datasets incorporate user information on other platforms. The “Million Musical Tweets Dataset (MMTD)” [7] provides a considerable source of music listening behavior that includes geographic, temporal, and other contextual information. In contrast to the MSD and “Yahoo! Music” dataset, which do not incorporate much information about the listeners, the MMTD is composed of the temporal and spatial information of microblog user’s listening history, such as longitude, latitude, date, and hour. Another similar dataset is “#nowplaying Music Dataset” [8], which also gathers user’s music listening behavior information from Twitter. Because the #nowplaying Music Dataset doesn’t focus on the spatial characteristic of tweets that largely restricts the amount of usable data, it collected approximately 50 million listening events (1 million for MMTD). The size of the dataset allows for analyzing music preference on a larger scale.

The aforementioned datasets don't offer much detailed user-specific information. So intending to delve into more personalized music taste, we still need other datasets. O. Celma *et al.* [9] collected data from Last.fm API and presented two music recommendation datasets, one containing about 360 thousand users' play counts of the artists they frequently listened to, the other containing nearly 1 thousand users' listening events, including the timestamp, artist, and song name. Both of the two datasets provide detailed user profile on Last.fm, such as gender, age, country, and sign up date. The most recent dataset is the "LFM-1b dataset" [10] presented by M. Schedl. Also acquiring data from Last.fm, the LFM-1b dataset greatly enriches the information. It offers over 1 billion listening events of approximately 120 thousand users, with more additional user-specific descriptors. Considering its substantial size and detailed information, the LFM-1b dataset is ideal to be used for user-aware and multimodal approaches to music retrieval, for example, the age-related music preference that we discuss in this paper.

2.2 Music preference and age

Previous studies investigating the relationship between music preferences and age usually concentrate on one specific age group, either the young or old ages. This is partly because the samples of these studies are university students from where the researchers work [11].

Albeit the age homogeneity of the samples, most of the studies indicate that age is highly influential on people's music taste. For example, J. Harrison and J. Ryan [1] analyzed the United States National Survey of Public Participation in the Arts (SPPA), mainly focusing on older adults' music genre preferences, and found that young people aged 18-24 and seniors older than 55 have significant differences in their music tastes. The young adults preferred rap, metal, rock, country, and blues, while older adults liked gospel, country, mood/easy listening, rock, and classical/chamber music, in which only two genres, rock and country, were shared by both age groups. They further pointed out that at older ages there was a negative correlation between the number of music tastes and age according to their results. Another study on mu-

music genre preferences and age was implemented by A. C. North and D. J. Hargreaves [12]. They conducted a survey of 2532 participants and found that fashionable musical style (e.g. hip-hop/rap, DJ-based music, dance, indie, chart pop) were more appreciated by young age group; conventional musical style (e.g. classical music, sixties pop, musicals, country) were favored by old age group. A. Bonneville-Roussy *et al.* [13] further conceptualized 21 music genres into 5 dimensions according to human's general perception and studied the age trends regarding them. The results revealed that preferences for dimensions "Mellow" (e.g. electronica/dance, world, and new age), "Unpretentious" (e.g. pop, country, and religious), and "Sophisticated" (e.g. blues, jazz, bluegrass, folk, classical, opera, and gospel) increased with age, whereas preferences for "Intense" (e.g. rock, punk, alternative, and heavy metal) and "Contemporary" (e.g. rap, soul/R&B, funk, and reggae) declined. In this way, they put the age differences in music preferences in a psychosocial framework and personality context, which inspired the following studies from a perspective of the social psychology of music.

Aside from that certain age group show specific music genre preference, the life course also plays an important role in the formation and development of one's music taste, given that social networks, family socialization, and education all have influences on music taste [1]. For example, during the early stage of life, teenagers trying to fit into a social group may adopt music preferences similar to that of the group, considering that they value both friendship and music [11]. M. Selfhout *et al.* [14] studied same-sex friends' music preferences. They gathered questionnaire data from 283 Dutch same-sex best friends of adolescents and found that highly similar music preferences were shared between friends. They surveyed the same participants twice in one year. The results suggested that adolescents who had similar music preferences that were not associated with the most mainstream music genres were more likely to become friends, but such similarity was not related to friendship stability. Regarding family and education factors, Ter Bogt *et al.* [15] investigated the continuity in music taste from parents to their children. They studied the music preferences of 325 adolescents and both their parents. Unsurprisingly, their analysis revealed that the education levels of both generations were linked to taste; and

parental preferences predicted adolescent music choices. Although these two studies mentioned above are biased towards young ages, they still helped us understand the trajectory of music tastes during the life course. Also, Holbrook and Schindler's 1989 study [16] suggested that music taste formation occurs during adolescence and early adulthood stages and remains stable throughout one's lifetime. However, by replicating Holbrook and Schindler's study, J. Hemming [17] pointed out the limitations of the original study, and that alternative research strategies as well as further data are needed.

It is worth noting that most of the studies above adopted data from questionnaire surveys, which were usually restricted to a certain area or group of people. As we mentioned in the previous section, some MIR datasets provide researchers with rich data of users' listening behavior and demographic information, which allows for large scale researches on music preferences and age. In a more recent study by Markus Schedl and Christine Bauer [2], they exploited the LFM-1b dataset and investigated the music genre preferences of 6-18 years old Last.fm users. Thanks to the substantial amount of data, they were able to uncover differences in both preferences and homogeneity between more fine-grained age groups, also countries and gender of the young population.

Markus Schedl and Christine Bauer's data-driven work greatly inspired this thesis. In our study, we also explore the LFM-1b dataset and analyze the data of different age groups. On the other hand, most of the previous work concentrated on music genres, which are not conceptualized enough to discuss from the human perceptive level. Therefore, our study also utilizes other forms of data that describe the acoustic information of music. Still, these relevant studies provide us with valuable notions on the relationship between music preferences and age.

2.3 Hit song prediction

Another topic that is related to music preferences and age is the hit song prediction task, which studies the reasons behind the success of a song. On the one hand, it

aims to understand what acoustic features represent the salient properties of popular songs. The methods used in hit song prediction tasks and the results of related work are worthy of reference. On the other hand, because music fashion changes over time, the trends of popular music may also help understand different generations' musical tastes.

Two main factors are involved with the success of a song: institutional factor (e.g. artist, record label, advertising, etc.) and consumer factor (consumer's choices and tastes) [18]. We mostly review the studies that focused on the latter factor, because they usually provided insights into musical properties such as loudness, tempo, valence, etc. These properties are considered to outweigh the effect of artist, label, and genre affiliation [19]. The early work of Dhanaraj and Logan [20] concentrated on the timbre aspects of hit songs. They made use of the Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCC) and conducted a hit song classification task on an in-house database of approximately 18,500 songs. Their result was better than random, indicating the timbre features are indeed related to whether a song will appear in music charts. In contrast, Frieler *et al.* [21] implemented another hit song classification experiment and obtained a rather poor result. They experimented with melodic features (pitch, interval, rhythm, meter, etc.) extracted from 266 pop songs in the UK charts. The classification result was at an accuracy of 52.6%, which just slightly exceeded the random baseline. They argued that melodic features alone are not sufficient to predict a hit song. Other studies giving promising results include Fan and Casey [22], and Herremans *et al.* [23], which both incorporated more audio features such as danceability, duration, energy, key, loudness, mode, tempo, and time signature. The latter one also used more advanced features that capture the temporal aspect which further improved the quality of their classification model.

More recent work employed deep learning techniques, for example, the studies of Yang *et al.* [24] and Yu *et al.* [25]. However, compared with the studies mentioned above, they didn't use many forms of audio features, only Mel-spectrogram. Recently, Zangerle *et al.* [26] enriched the features with more low- and high-level acoustic information and again made use of a deep neural network. Their result

showed that the combination of these two types of features in their proposed network architecture improved the prediction performance, and the most significant features are about mood and voice. In our thesis, we use very similar features and the work of Zangerle *et al.* provides us with an enlightening example of exploring these features.

Most of the previous work aforementioned viewed hit song prediction as a regression (or rating) or classification problem with various approaches, including SVM classifiers. This thesis extends the same methodology to the music preference topic and provides a new perspective on this problem.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter, we introduce the materials, the approach to extract samples from the dataset, the method to select the most relevant features, and how we conduct the classification task to validate the results of feature selection.

3.1 Materials

In our study, we jointly take advantage of multiple dataset and databases. Particularly, we use the LFM-1b dataset to collect the listening events of each generation and, MusicBrainz and AcousticBrainz for musical data.

3.1.1 The LFM-1b dataset

As mentioned in Chapter 2, the LFM-1b dataset [10] is a large scale dataset for music information retrieval and recommendation systems. As the name suggests, it contains more than one billion (1,088,161,692) individual listening events acquired from the music platform Last.fm. These listening events are created by 120,175 users of the Last.fm. Each listening event is characterized by artist, album, and track name, and further includes a timestamp.

Furthermore, the dataset provides demographic data of the users, which makes it particularly suitable for user-aware MIR tasks. These demographic data includes

user's country, age, gender, and registered timestamp, among which we are mostly interested in the age information. Out of these 120,175 users, 46,120 (38.4%) provide age information in their profile. Figure 1 illustrates the age distribution of this subset of users. Obviously, the age distribution is quite non-uniform and skewed towards the left, which indicates that the majority of the Last.fm users are young. More precisely, the age distribution has an arithmetic mean at 25.4 years, a standard deviation of 9.7, a median of 23, and 25- and 75-percentile, respectively, at 20 and 28 years.

Figure 1: The age distribution of the LFM-1b dataset [10]

Based on the age information, we divide these 46,120 users into the three aforementioned sociological generations: Generation X, 5538 users; Generation Y, 37028 users; Generation Z, 3564 users. For those users who were born before 1965 (the Me Generation, or Baby Boomers), we actually also include them into the Generation X because they only make up a very small part of the data.

3.1.2 MusicBrainz and AcousticBrainz

Our thesis aims to study the music preferences from an acoustic perspective. To this end, we exploit two open databases, MusicBrainz and AcousticBrainz.

MusicBrainz

MusicBrainz¹ is an open music encyclopedia that collects user-submitted music metadata and makes it available to the public. The metadata includes song information such as artists, releases group, albums, recordings, releases, etc. Each of these items is assigned with a MusicBrainz Identifier (MBID), a 36-character universally unique identifier. The MBIDs for recordings also work as indexes in AcousticBrainz for retrieving acoustic features.

With the track names and artist names we collect in the LFM-1b dataset, we can query the corresponding MBIDs through the MusicBrainz API. These MBIDs are later used to fetch acoustic data from the AcousticBrainz.

AcousticBrainz

AcousticBrainz [27] is a database of acoustic features extracted from all kinds of music by the Essentia toolkit [28], a well established and widely used extraction library for audio descriptors. It stores two levels of acoustic features: low-level and high-level. The low-level features include acoustic descriptors characterizing overall loudness, dynamics and spectral shape of a signal, rhythm descriptors (including beats per minute), and tonal information (including keys and scales). The high-level features, on the other hand, include information about moods, genres, vocals, and music types computed from low-level features by pre-trained classifiers.

In our study, we mainly make use of the low-level features that have one single mean value, and high-level features that only have two classes. These features are shown in Table 1, including 59 low-levels and 12 high-levels (the low-level features are further divided into three subsets, spectral low-level, rhythm, and tonal).

¹<https://musicbrainz.org/>

Feature class	Features
low-level	<p>low-level (spectral): barkbands_crest, barkbands_flatness_db, barkbands_kurtosis, barkbands_skewness, barkbands_spread, average_loudness, dynamic_complexity, erbbands_crest, erbbands_flatness_db, erbbands_kurtosis, erbbands_skewness, erbbands_spread, hfc, melbands_crest, melbands_flatness_db, melbands_kurtosis, melbands_skewness, melbands_spread, pitch_salience, silence_rate_20dB, silence_rate_30dB, silence_rate_60dB, spectral_centroid, spectral_complexity, spectral_decrease, spectral_energy, spectral_energyband_high, spectral_energyband_low, spectral_energyband_middle_high, spectral_energyband_middle_low, spectral_entropy, spectral_flux, spectral_kurtosis, spectral_rms, spectral_rolloff, spectral_skewness, spectral_spread, spectral_strongpeak, zerocrossingrate, dissonance,</p> <p>rhythm: beats_loudness, bpm, danceability, onset_rate, bpm_histogram_first_peak_bpm, bpm_histogram_first_peak_spread, bpm_histogram_first_peak_weight, bpm_histogram_second_peak_bpm, bpm_histogram_second_peak_spread, bpm_histogram_second_peak_weight,</p> <p>tonal: chords_changes_rate, key_strength, chords_number_rate, chords_strength, hpcp_entropy, tuning_diatonic_strength, tuning_nontempered_energy_ratio, tuning_equal_tempered_deviation, tuning_frequency</p>
high-level	<p>danceability, gender, mood_acoustic, mood_aggressive, mood_electronic, mood_happy, mood_party, mood_relaxed, mood_sad, timbre, tonal_atonal, voice_instrumental</p>

Table 1: Acoustic features retrieved from the AcousticBrainz

3.2 Data acquisition

To characterize the music preferences on a user level, we gather the most frequently listened songs of each generation by computing the user’s playcount. To this end, we parse the listening events data of the LFM-1b dataset and count how many times each user plays the songs that he or she once listened to. By summing up the playcounts of users that belong to the same generation, we obtain three song lists ranked by the total playcount. We further select the top 2000 songs in each ranking list and remove the songs that appear in multiple lists because we are not interested in just popular songs, but we are interested in popular ones that don’t appear in another generation. This deduplication also avoids the multi-label problem in the later classification task. We also check the data availability of each song in the MusicBrainz because some of the songs don’t exist in it (e.g. ocean waves white noise) and don’t have corresponding acoustic features in the AcousticBrainz. After deduplication and cleansing, there are 951 songs left for Generation X, 460 for Generation Y, and 809 for Generation Z. We then select the same amount (460) of songs from each list as final samples so that our data is balanced. Based on the song names and artist names, we query the MBIDs of these songs from the MusicBrainz and retrieve their acoustic features from the AcousticBrainz. We also acquire the release year information provided by the MusicBrainz metadata. Our final samples are 1380 songs with a 72-dimensional (49 low-levels, 12 high-levels, and release year) feature vector.

3.3 Feature selection

To find the features that are more related to the music preference of each generation, we adopt a common method for univariate feature selection, F-test.

F-test: F-test is an important technique for the analysis of variance (ANOVA) [29]. It computes the ANOVA F-value to estimate the degree of linear dependency between two variables, in our case, each feature and generation. Higher F-value means higher dependency.

For each of the 72 features (including the release year), we implement the F-test to measure their correlation with the generation differences. The F-values and rank of features are shown in the next chapter. We further calculate the mean values of the top features regarding each generation, which allows for revealing the trends of generations' preferences on these features.

3.4 Generation classification

To verify that the higher ranking features are indeed more correlated to the generation differences than the lower ranking ones, we conduct a generation classification experiment with the Support Vector Machine (SVM) as the classifier.

Support vector machines: SVMs are classic standard machine learning classifiers [30]. They are widely used in many classification and regression tasks. It aims to find decision boundaries between each class of data points. The decision boundaries are also called hyperplanes, and the data points that are close to the hyperplanes are support vectors. The distance between the support vectors on both sides of the hyperplanes is the “margin”. During the classifier training process, the margin between two classes is expected to be maximized, so that the SVMs classifier performs better on predicting which class a new data point belongs to.

SVMs have several advantages that make them suitable for our experiment. First, they exhibit a great ability to generalize given a small training corpus, compared with deep learning techniques, which achieve great success recently but require massive data. Secondly, they are particularly suitable for learning in high dimensional spaces. In our study, our available data is limited; each song has a 72-dimensional feature vector. Therefore, SVMs classifier is ideal for this generation classification task.

In our experiment, we first use the release year data as a baseline. It has been shown in the study of Zangerle *et al.* [26] that the release year of track greatly contributes to the hit song prediction model, improving every experiment by 12–13%. Considering it's not an acoustic feature we are especially interested in, we regard it as a reasonable baseline which allows for comparison with other acoustic features. Besides, since we

have three balance classes, the random baseline of balance ternary classification is also involved in the comparison. We then experiment with different combinations of the acoustic features, such as all acoustic features, only low-/high-level features, each subset of the low-level features, etc. All input data is standardized to between 0 and 1. For the evaluation and comparison of different feature combinations, we calculate the classification accuracy and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC AUC).

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, we present the findings of our experiments, including the best features determined by the F-test, general trends of the top-ranking features, and the results of generation classification.

4.1 Feature selection results

Feature	F-value	Ranking
spectral_complexity	72.21	1
spectral_energyband_middle_high	71.68	2
barkbands_spread	65.82	3
mood_sad	62.72	4
mood_acoustic	61.07	5
timbre	53.53	6
spectral_flux	50.7	7
spectral_entropy	45.73	8
tuning_frequency	44.79	9
spectral_energyband_high	43.06	10

Table 2: Top 10 features with the highest F-values

The feature selection experiments aimed to rank all the acoustic features based on

their relevance to the different generations' music preferences. We conducted F-test on each feature and compute the F-value. Table 2 lists the 10 features that have the highest scores. The ranking of all the 72 features is shown in Table 4 in the Appendix.

Figure 2: The mean values of the top 10 features for three generations

To further investigate generations' tastes in the top 10 features, we calculated the mean values and plot their trends, as shown in Figure 2. We can identify some trends of these features over the generation changing. For example, `spectral_complexity` and `barkbands_spread` tend to increase as the generation becomes younger; while

mood_sad and mood_acoustic decrease. In the next chapter, we will discuss some of these features and interpret the trends in detail.

4.2 Generation classification results

Feature	ROC AUC	Accuracy
year (baseline)	0.5892	39.73%
all acoustic features	0.7380	53.27%
all features	0.7506	54.14%
all features (LP)	0.7057	52.11%
all features (HP)	0.7448	53.82%
high-level	0.7098	50.45%
high-level (LP)	0.6435	47.60%
high-level (HP)	0.6662	48.43%
low-level	0.7238	53.46%
low-level (LP)	0.7151	51.86%
low-level (HP)	0.7285	55.14%
low-level - rhythm	0.6285	42.77%
low-level - tonal	0.6541	47.53%
low-level - spectral low-level	0.6688	52.55%
low-level - spectral low-level (LP)	0.6962	48.87%
low-level - spectral low-level (HP)	0.7194	53.47%

Table 3: Results for generation prediction on different feature combinations

The classification experiment aimed to compare the contribution to the performance of the classifier made by different subsets of features. The results of the experiment are presented in Table 3. Theoretically, the features with higher F-values are more relevant to the generation differences thus contribute more to the distinguishing power of the classifier and vice versa. We verify this expected result by inputting feature subsets that are either without top-ranking features (low ranking pass, hereinafter “LP”) or without bottom-ranking features (high ranking pass, hereinafter “HP”). Here are the contents of each feature subsets in detail:

- **year**: the release years of tracks extracted from the music metadata.
- **all acoustic features**: all the 71 low- and high-level acoustic features presented in Table 1.
- **all features**: all the 72 features we collect, consisting of the low- and high-level acoustic features as well as the release years.
- **all features (LP)**: all features without the top 10.
- **all features (HP)**: all features without the bottom 10.
- **high-level**: only the 12 high-level acoustic features presented in Table 1.
- **high-level (LP)**: 9 high-level acoustic features without the top 3.
- **high-level (HP)**: 9 high-level acoustic features without the bottom 3.
- **low-level**: only the 59 low-level acoustic features presented in Table 1.
- **low-level (LP)**: 49 low-level acoustic features without the top 10.
- **low-level (HP)**: 49 low-level acoustic features without the bottom 10.
- **low-level – rhythm**: a subset of the low-level features, consisting of the 10 rhythm features as presented in Table 1.
- **low-level – tonal**: a subset of the low-level features, consisting of the 9 tonal features as presented in Table 1.
- **low-level – spectral low-level**: a subset of the low-level features, consisting of the 40 spectral low-level features as presented in Table 1.
- **low-level – spectral low-level (LP)**: 30 spectral low-level features without the top 10 .
- **low-level – spectral low-level (HP)**: 30 spectral low-level features without the bottom 10.

According to Table 3, the classification accuracies are rather low: at around 50%, slightly exceeding the random baseline (33.33%) and the release year baseline (39.73%). Still, the results are to some extent as expected and we can draw useful conclusions from them. For example, all “HP” subsets have better results than their corresponding “LP” subsets, proving that high ranking features contribute more to the performance of the classifier. Therefore, the high ranking features are indeed more relevant to the generation differences. We further discuss Table 3 in the next chapter.

Figure 3: Confusion matrix of the classification using all features

We also plot the confusion matrices of the classification results to inspect the generation differences. For example, Figure 3 depicts the result of the classification with all the 72 features. Despite the weak classification accuracy of this group in Table 3, the correct inference rates of Generation X and Generation Z are obviously higher than the average accuracy. This also provides us with helpful information in the following discussion.

Chapter 5

Discussion

The experiment results presented in Chapter 4 suggest that different acoustic features have varying degrees of impact on different generations' music preferences. Moreover, many of the high ranking features are shown to obey certain trends along with the generation changing. In this chapter, we discuss the findings in detail. We first evaluate the generation classification results, analyzing the contribution made by each feature class to the classifier performance. Then we delve into the most relevant features, interpreting the meanings of the features and investigating the trends in tastes of different generations.

5.1 Generation Classification

The objective of the generation classification is to observe to what extent the relevant features make a difference to the performance of the classifier. We assume that the high ranking features should contribute more to the classification result. Table 3 confirms this assumption. First, any unfiltered feature class is superior to the corresponding "LP" subset. For example, "all features" beats "all features (LP)". Moreover, all the "HP" groups also outperform the corresponding "LP" ones. Therefore, the high ranking features indeed provide more distinguishing power to the SVMs classifier, indicating the features with high F-values are more relevant to generations' music preferences.

What needs to be emphasized here is that we didn't expect the feature selection to help the SVMs classifier perform better by removing the low ranking (or uncorrelated) features. In other words, only using the higher ranking features doesn't necessarily improve the classification results. In Table 3, although "low-level (HP)" and "spectral low-level (HP)" outperform "low-level" and "spectral low-level" respectively, unfiltered "all features" and "high-level" have better results than their HP-filtered counterparts. Theoretically, removing the redundant or irrelevant features could simplify the model and enhance generalization as well as reduce computing time. However, the generalization performance of the SVMs classifier is independent of the dimensionality of the feature space. The SVMs classifier uses regularization to avoid over-fitting so it is generally robust to noise. In our cases, there are not too many features. Even if the low ranking features introduce noises, the negative effect may be limited.

When comparing the results of different feature classes, we can observe that the highest accuracy value of 55.14% is achieved by using the "low-level (HP)" features, and the highest ROC AUC of 0.7506 is achieved by using "all features". Generally, the more feature classes we input to the SVMs classifier, the better the result. In our study, the low-level features, especially the spectral low-level features, seem to contribute more to the distinguishing power. This is because that not only do they make up the majority of all features, but also half of the spectral low-level features rank top 40% in Table 4. In contrast, the "rhythm" subset has only 10 features and most of them have rather low F-values. Unsurprisingly, the rhythm feature subset achieves the lowest ROC AUC and accuracy values of 0.6285 and 42.77%.

As we mentioned in Chapter 4, the classification accuracies of the SVMs classifier are not very high. However, considering the release year baseline accuracy at 39.73% and the random baseline accuracy at 33.33%, the acoustic features to a certain extent improved the classifier performance. Similarly, when it comes to the ROC AUC, the four best results in our experiment, though still quite poor, exceeded the release year baseline at 0.5892 and a random guess baseline at 0.6667. Two possible explanations come to mind. First, this generation classification task is somewhat an

ill-defined problem. The three generations we used as labels are not distinguishable enough. Especially when two generations are contiguous, they may share more similarities in music preference. In our study, even though we have deduplicated the songs in each generation’s song list, the feature clusters still greatly overlap without a distinct boundary, in which case the SVMs could not find the perfect hyperplane to separate each cluster. However, the overlap of feature clusters is smaller when two generations are not contiguous, e.g. Generation X and Generation Z. Therefore, we would expect the SVMs classifier to show better distinguishing power between these two generations. Figure 3 is in line with our expectation: in the confusion matrix, Generation X and Generation Z have higher correct inference rates, while Generation Y is poorly classified. Thus the overall classification results are rather weak. The second potential explanation might be due to the limitations in our study, mostly the flaws in our dataset. We will talk about the limitation at the end of this chapter.

5.2 Relevant features and preference trends

So far we have actually answered our first research question: we found certain acoustic features and proved that they are more related to the music preference of each generation. These features are the top features in Table 4. In this section, we try to answer the second research question, why do different generations have different tastes in them. To this end, we will intuitively interpret these features, mostly the top 10 features, as well as their trends, and take other potential factors into account.

The top 1 feature is `spectral_complexity`, which describes the complexity of the audio signal based on the number of peaks in the signal’s spectrum [31]. Spectral complexity could represent the happy mood and relaxed mood of music. Generally, happy songs tend to have higher spectral complexity, while relaxed songs usually are spectrally less complex. According to Figure 2, the mean value of spectral complexity has an upward trend. This indicates that the young generation tends to listen to songs that are more “happy” and less “relaxed”. This would be in line with

the findings by M. Interiano *et al.* [32], who studied the trends of successful music and reported that there is a tendency of being more “happy” and less “relaxed” for successful rock music, and rock music is shown to be preferred more by young listeners compared to adults [2]. We further inspected the two high-level features `mood_happy` and `mood_relaxed`. Although ranked quite low, their trends are consistent with the spectral complexity. Therefore, it is reasonable that songs with higher spectral complexity are generally more in line with young generation’s tastes.

The second and tenth features in Table 2, `spectral_energyband_middle_high` and `spectral_energyband_high`, both depict the energy in the middle- to high-frequency band of the input audio. These two features reflect the loudness of music to some extent, as loudness and energy intensity are positively correlated [33]. In Figure 2, we can observe that they both tend to increase as generation become younger, suggesting the loudness could have a similar trend. We attribute this increasing loudness to the tendency of the music industry. With a common belief of “louder is better”, music industry is squeezing more and more loudness into recordings by over compressing dynamics, which is called “loudness war” [34]. Since the newly released “louder” songs are listened more by the young generation, it’s not surprising that the spectral energy in the middle- to high-frequency band also goes up as generation becomes younger. We also inspected the other two similar but low ranking features, `spectral_energyband_low` and `spectral_energyband_middle_low`. However, they don’t show obvious trends. The reason why higher frequency band energy is more salient than the lower still remains to be discussed. One possible explanation could be the development of music production that allows for more space for the high-frequency component. Moreover, both of the trend of feature `gender` in our study and the findings of Interiano *et al.* [32] suggested a more “female” trend, which could be another potential explanation.

The third feature in Table 2, `barkbands_spread`, measures the average spread, or statistical dispersion, of the Bark scale spectrum in relation to its centroid. It describes how noise-like a signal is. Noisy sounds are expected to have a higher spectrum spread, while individual tonal sounds with isolated peaks will result in a

low spectral spread. In Figure 2, the mean value of this feature increases as the generation becomes younger, implying the music listened by the young generation tends to be noisier, or more distorted and aggressive. This trend is in line with the finding of A. Bonneville-Roussy *et al.*, who categorized such kind of music genres like rock, punk, and heavy metal as dimension Intense, and revealed that preference for this dimension decreases with age [13]. This result can be interpreted from two perspectives. On the one hand, adolescents are experiencing the life stage of developing self-consciousness and sense of independence, thus they might be attracted to these noisy music genres out of their rebelliousness. On the other hand, there is evidence showing that as people are getting older, the auditory system would gradually decline, leading to less tolerance to the intense volume changes of noisy music [35]. We also noticed that two high-level features, `mood_aggressive` and `tonal_atonal` (ranked 45 and 12 respectively), describe very similar musical characteristics. Unsurprisingly, we found the same tendency in them.

The fourth to sixth features in Table 2 are high-level features and they are more intuitive. First, feature `mood_sad` depicts the sadness of a song. In our study, the higher value means a higher possibility of “sad”. Second, feature `mood_acoustic` determines whether a song is “acoustic”, and the higher value means a higher possibility of “acoustic”. Third, feature `timbre` measures whether a song sounds “bright” or “dark”. The timbre of a song with a higher value should sound brighter. According to Figure 2, younger generations tend to listen to songs that are less “sad”, less “acoustic”, and less “bright”. The less “sad” trend is somehow in agreement with the more “happy” trend aforementioned. The less “acoustic” trend could be attributed to the differences in genre preferences. Genres like rock, punk, metal, alternative, R&B, etc. that preferred by younger generation [2] are obviously less acoustic than the genres preferred by older generations, such as jazz, blues, folk, classical, etc [13]. The reason for the less “bright” timbre is not straightforward. The brightness of timbre is associated with the spectral centroid of the signal: the timbre sounds less bright with the spectral centroid decreasing. However, we found that the trend of the feature `spectral_centroid` (ranked 16 in Table 4) is increasing. This contradiction remains to be discussed.

Another acoustic feature worth discussing in Table 2 is `spectral_entropy`. The entropy measures the uncertainty or unpredictability of a probability mass function (PMF). When applied to spectrum, entropy can be used to quantify the peak distribution of the spectrum [36]. It has been used for automatic speech detection. In general, the spectral entropy should be lower for music frames than for speech frames [37]. Interestingly, Figure 2 shows an upward trend of the `spectral_entropy`, implying young generations listen to more songs that are more “vocal”. This result is also consistent with our findings of the trend of feature `voice_instrumental`. We interpret this trend from the following two aspects. First, the vocal is indeed a salient factor for a listener to decide whether to like or dislike a track [38], and it helps evoke the listener’s emotion toward the music which is also important to musical preferences [39]. Second, the prevalent of rap music among adolescents [2] is unneglectable. This highly vocal music genre to a certain extent contributes to the upward trend of `spectral_entropy`.

5.3 Limitation and future work

As we mentioned above, there are some limitations in our dataset. The LFM-1b dataset may not necessarily accurately represent the music preferences of every generation. First, the age distribution is not balance according to Figure 1. We assigned 37028 users as Generation Y, but only 5538 and 3564 users as Generation X and Generation Z respectively. After the data deduplication and cleansing, the insufficient data of Generation X and Generation Z became even scarcer. Therefore, the samples we used might not be able to represent the characteristics of these two generations, further causing the SVMs classifier to perform poorly. Secondly, it could be problematic to extract the playcount from the LFM-1b dataset. Because the highly active users of Last.fm tend to listen to tracks by their personal favorite artists over and over again, while occasional and seldom listeners tend to play only a few tracks by their preferred artists. Consequently, the playcount rank might not necessarily generalize to the music preference of a whole generation, especially for Generation X and Generation Z, which are not robust enough because of their

low sample size. In future work, a more generalized dataset is needed, and the generation division could be more fine-grained. Regarding the representation of music preferences, a more reasonable matrix is also necessary.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

In this thesis, we studied the music preferences of different generations from an acoustic perspective. We jointly utilize multiple dataset and databases: the Last.fm dataset for user’s listening events and, MusicBrainz and AcousticBrainz for acoustic features as well as music metadata. 71 low- and high-level acoustic features plus the release year information of tracks were collected. Among these features, we used F-test to select features that are the most relevant to each generation’s music preference. We further implemented a generation classification experiment to compare the contribution of different subsets of features. Although the accuracies of the classifier were not quite high, this experiment proved that the higher ranking features in F-test were indeed more relevant to each generation’s music preference since they contributed more to the distinguishing power of classifier. We also investigate the statistical data of the top features and revealed some trends of them over the changing generations. For example, low-level features like `spectral_complexity`, `spectral_energyband_high`, `barkbands_spread`, `spectral_entropy`, etc. had upward trends as the generation became younger, while for high-level features such as `mood_sad`, `mood_acoustic`, and `timbre`, younger generation preferred songs that were less “sad”, less “acoustic”, and less bright. Some other trends may related to `mood_happy`, `mood_relaxed`, `gender`, `average_loudness`, etc. We further interpreted the trends of these features intuitively. The findings of our study might

provide some insights into the differences in generations and the trends of musical tastes. Our study was from an acoustic perspective, which is also an extension of previous studies that were mostly based on a genre level.

List of Figures

1	The age distribution of the LFM-1b dataset [10]	12
2	The mean values of the top 10 features for three generations	19
3	Confusion matrix of the classification using all features	22

List of Tables

1	Acoustic features retrieved from the AcousticBrainz	14
2	Top 10 features with the highest F-values	18
3	Results for generation prediction on different feature combinations . .	20
4	F-values and rankings of all features	39

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Appendix A

First Appendix

Table 4: F-values and rankings of all features

Feature	F-value	Ranking
spectral_complexity	72.21	1
spectral_energyband_middle_high	71.68	2
barkbands_spread	65.82	3
mood_sad	62.72	4
mood_acoustic	61.07	5
timbre	53.53	6
spectral_flux	50.7	7
spectral_entropy	45.73	8
tuning_frequency	44.79	9
spectral_energyband_high	43.06	10
tuning_equal_tempered_deviation	40.39	11
tonal_atonal	38.21	12
average_loudness	37.68	13
barkbands_flatness_db	37.45	14
spectral_rms	37.31	15
spectral_centroid	36.08	16

Continuation of Table 4		
Feature	F-value	Ranking
tuning_nontempered_energy_ratio	33.35	17
erbbands_flatness_db	32.5	18
hpcp_entropy	32.44	19
melbands_spread	30.95	20
dissonance	30.39	21
onset_rate	29.29	22
zerocrossingrate	28.73	23
erbbands_crest	24.62	24
melbands_flatness_db	22.96	25
spectral_energy	22.83	26
spectral_rolloff	21.76	27
hfc	20.35	28
erbbands_skewness	19.87	29
dynamic_complexity	17.72	30
silence_rate_60dB	17.07	31
spectral_decrease	14.65	32
spectral_energyband_low	14.63	33
chords_changes_rate	14.63	34
mood_electronic	14.24	35
tuning_diatonic_strength	13.29	36
melbands_crest	12.91	37
spectral_spread	12.22	38
chords_strength	11.32	39
danceability	11.28	40
mood_party	10.78	41
beats_loudness	10.25	42
erbbands_kurtosis	9.98	43
mood_relaxed	7.68	44

Continuation of Table 4		
Feature	F-value	Ranking
mood_aggressive	7.53	45
spectral_energyband_middle_low	7.25	46
key_strength	6.72	47
bpm_histogram_first_peak_weight	6.43	48
year	5.36	49
barkbands_crest	5.24	50
bpm_histogram_first_peak_spread	5.2	51
voice_instrumental	5.1	52
mood_happy	3.81	53
chords_number_rate	3.48	54
silence_rate_30dB	3.13	55
silence_rate_20dB	2.71	56
gender	1.95	57
pitch_salience	1.69	58
spectral_strongpeak	1.6	59
spectral_kurtosis	1.02	60
barkbands_kurtosis	1.0	61
spectral_skewness	0.82	62
erbbands_spread	0.7	63
barkbands_skewness	0.57	64
danceability	0.57	65
bpm	0.29	66
melbands_skewness	0.28	67
bpm_histogram_first_peak_bpm	0.24	68
bpm_histogram_second_peak_spread	0.23	69
bpm_histogram_second_peak_bpm	0.16	70
melbands_kurtosis	0.09	71
bpm_histogram_second_peak_weight	0.09	72